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EMERGING ASPECTS OF AIFOR SMART LIFE

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ABSTRACT- Nowadays Artificial intelligence makes our life easy and comfortable that is hard to imagine that to survive our life without AI technology. We all know that AI is a precious gift to human being. Recently it is used in robotics, education, agriculture, computer vision, cyber security, face recognition, speech recognition, self driving cars, medical image processing, biometrics, bioinformatics, satellite control, disease detection, drugs development, network developments, manufacturing, business, healthcare and medicine. In the digital era AI provides the best results in all most all the domains. This article helps to understand the emerging aspects of AI in various fields.

Keywords - [Artificial Intelligence, Agriculture, Deep Learning, Medicine, Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, Robotics.]

1. INTRODUCTION

We need intelligence to solve a particular problem in efficient manner. Like human being machines having Artificial Intelligence (AI) can do thinking, learning, reasoning, makes meaning fuldecisions and solves the complex problem efficiently [1].

In the digital world smart machine sarevery much useful in our daily routine tasks; they become the needs of our life. Without a doubt, most things belongs to us are applications of AI such as smart phones, Air conditioners, Digital cameras, videogames, traffic lights, refrigerators, self driving cars, drones, robots, autonomous vehicles and machine setc. These applications of AI are work on a “smart” technology. AI is alatest growing technology that makes our work very simple. We know that today’s smart machines work millions of times faster thanearlier machines.

Recentlymanyresearchesaregoingbasedon Machinelearning (ML) thatisasubdivisi on of AI. It Machine learning algorithm is used in the social networking site for example most of the busines people use Facebook for their products and services developments. At present DLis the recentmostgrowingresearchareas. DL algorithm

sarewidelyusedindiseasediagnosis, drugsdevelopment, machinetranslation, objectidentification, in dustrialauto mation, marketing research, medicalre search, social network filtering, image recognition and sentimentanalys is and soon [2]. The following diagram Figure.1 presents the subset of Artificialintelligence.

Figure.1 : Subset of Artificial Intelligence

Advantages of AI

Makes the system stolearnautomaticallyandget Hand lelarge volume of data:

Machine can handle better from the irexperience. ML is used to teach Machines the way to handle the data more efficiently. Wecanseethe machinelearning algorithm sareused in our dailyroutineapplications. For example the popular searchenginesuchas Goog leworksonmachine learning algorithm basis. In addition, largevolumesofstructuredandunstructureddataeasily. Reduce the errors: Unlike humans smart machinesdonotmakemistakes.Mostlyitprovidestheaccuratean derrorfree result.

- Save our precious time:Smart machines canperform any types of work rapidly so it saves ourprecioustime.
- Diligence:Unlike human being machine does notgettiredandfeleboresoitcanworkfor24hours.
- Handleriskyjobeasily:Smartmachinescanhandlerisky jobveryefficiently.Forexamplerobots are used in bomb deactivation, Space andoceanexploration.
- Takethe decisions rapidly:Smart machine workswith much higher speed compared to humans andproducetheresultsina fasterway.

1. Disadvantages of AI

- **Makes Humans Lazy:** AI technology is making human being lazy because it automates the majority of the work. Nowadays humans are mostly relying on the smart machines that leads problem to future generations.
- **Unemployment:** AI technology replaces the robots for automation and risky job so it will create an unemployment problem. It affects the younger generation life.
- **Lack of creativity:** Machines can perform only the defined task that is written in the program by the user. It does not have creative thinking.
- **Expensive:** AI supporting machines required high expensive hardware and software. In addition we spend more money for maintenance [3].

1. Applications of AI

Fig.2: Applications of Artificial Intelligence

It is no doubt AI is used in numerous fields. Applications of Artificial intelligence are shown in Fig 2. Some of the widely used AI applications are given below.

Medicine

Nowadays the usage of Artificial intelligence is unavoidable in the field of medicine. AI is mostly used in most of the medical fields like Cardiology, neurology, embryology, etc. In recent years, ML algorithms are used to identify various diseases like cancer, brain tumor, malaria and dengue in earlier stage and also monitor the patient's health condition. For the last one year we are in COVID-19 Pandemic situations many researches are done to develop the drugs for Coronavirus. Computer vision is very valuable in the field of medicine. With the help of computer vision and signal processing technologies doctors can treat the patients remotely. Nowadays in most critical situation robots are used for treating the patient. It carries out hundreds of clinical tests simultaneously. It can do stitching more accurate than a human doctor. Mostly it is used for complex surgeries such as brain tumors to reduce the degree of error occur [4] [5].

Agriculture

In agriculture the advancements of AI is used to increase the crop yield also we can easily predict the time it takes for harvest the crop thus increasing efficiency of farming. In many countries Machine learning algorithms are used to monitor the quality of soil and crops. Computer vision algorithms are used to detect crop diseases in earlier stage so the farmers can take the appropriate decision quickly. Thus increase the production quality. Nowadays robots are used in plant crops, irrigation, weed control and in pest detection. Green house automation, simulation and optimization techniques are more specializations of AI in agriculture [6].

Education

Computers revolutionized the teaching field in many ways. Teachers make their notes presentation, educational quiz and videos easier. It helps the students to understand their subjects easily and more effectively. Intelligent tutoring systems increase the motivation and learning capabilities of student. Teachers use these smart and intelligent machines to prepare study materials, calculate grades, maintain attendance, access student data and evaluate student performance in online programs and assessments. Nowadays computers and internet are reused for students and researchers to improve their research and communication skills. It is no doubt each and every people use search engine to clear their doubts easily. During this COVID-19 pandemic period smartphones and computers with internet are works as a major tool for e-learning.

Natural Language Processing

Natural language processing is not a new one, in last few years it plays a crucial role in human and machine interactions. In addition, using NLP we can do translation, information retrieval, sentiment analysis, summarization, segmentation etc. NLP techniques depend on machine learning to understand human languages [7]. Robots are used in hazardous works like inspection of radioactive materials, bomb removal, space exploration and ocean exploration. It is very helpful in industries for handling material, cutting, welding, drilling, color coating, polishing, etc [8].

Computer Vision

The objective of Computer vision is to recognize the digital images. It is mostly used in medical imaging, biometrics, surveillance and object

Speech Recognition

Speech recognition is used to recognize phrases and words in our spoken language and translate it into a machine understandable format. Now a days it is used to compose a text message and convert the text message to speech. In today's technology-driven world various DL algorithms are used in Speech recognition.

Robotics

Robotics is one of the hottest subfields of AI that is used to design intelligent machines. Robotics is mostly used in military, medicine, industries, exploration etc. In the digital age robots are a boon for the people. Due to less blood loss, less pain and scarring, less recovery time and smaller risk of infection Robots are helps to the surgeons in complex surgery. recognition. In military to detect the enemy soldiers and send the missile to the specific target area this technology is used. Computer vision is used in medicine to measure the organ dimensions, blood flow and find the structure of brain.

In addition Computer Vision and ML also used to identify the tumor in brain or other parts of the body in earlier stage [5].

Biometrics

Nowadays Artificial intelligence with biometric technology is used by companies and governments in a variety of applications for identification. Emerging biometrics based identification is used in most of these security applications such as Banking security, ATM security, E-commerce etc.

Entertainment

Nowadays Artificial intelligence grabs user's attention in Entertainment. Using the advancement of AI technology we can play games, watch movies and sports with real effects. Today the Virtual reality technology and deep dreaming gives more interesting and immersive 3D visual experiences to the users in movies and games [9].

Manufacturing

AI plays an important role in Manufacturing. We know that drones and industrial robots have been playing a great role in manufacturing industry. AI with deep learning helps in manufacturing to lower the operational costs, increase the productivity and reduce the wastage of material. Machine learning algorithms and Complex AI algorithms like artificial neural networks are generating trustworthy predictions regarding the status of assets and machinery [10].

Conclusion

In the modern world AI is a great complement for the people. We can't imagine that a world without AI technology. AI makes our life smart. It has given precious life style for us. It is the reason behind the emerging development of AI. Nowadays there are no things without AI technology. In each and every place we can see the applications of artificial intelligence such as smart television, smart refrigerator, traffic light, self-driving car etc. Nowadays most of the research is going on AI technology. In few years it will reach a great status. It is for sure that Artificial Intelligence technology will rule the world in future.

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